

Cysteine as a Selective Reagent for Spectrophotometric Determination of Osmium(VIII)

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Cysteine forms a 1:1 coloured complex with Os^{VIII} in aqueous solution. The yellowish brown complex exhibits a maximum absorbance at 370 nm in the pH range 4.0-5.2. Beer's law is obeyed from 1.0-60.0 ppm, the optimum range being 5.0-55.0 ppm. The Sandell's sensitivity of the reaction is 0.132 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and the molar absorptivity of the complex is 1429 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$.

MOST of the methods reported in the literature involve the prior extraction of osmium-reagent complexes in organic solvents¹⁻⁶. These methods are very sensitive to variations in laboratory conditions. More recently, 1,5-diphenylcarbazine⁷, phenanthrene quinone monosemicarbazone⁸, rhodamine⁹, *N,N*-bis(hydroxy methyl)thiourea¹⁰ and 3-hydroxy-2-methyl-1,4-naphthaquinone monoxime¹¹ have been used for the spectrophotometric determinations of osmium(VIII) but are subjected to a large number of interferences and are applicable to a very small range of osmium concentrations. Cysteine provides not only a rapid method but has the advantage of being straight forward and less interfering. This method can also be used for the estimations in a larger range of concentrations.

Experimental

Absorbance measurements at varying wavelengths were recorded on a Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched glass cuvettes. Measurements of pH were made with an expanded scale (solid state) ECIL pH-823 pH meter.

All the chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade. Osmium tetroxide (Johnson Mathey) and cysteine hydrochloride (Koch-Light) were used as such. Acetic acid-sodium acetate buffers were used for pH adjustment. All the solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. The solution of metal ion was standardised by reported methods^{7,9}.

Results and Discussion

Selection of wavelength: Vosburgh and Cooper's method¹² was applied. The mixtures of the metal and the reagent in ratios 1:5, 1:6, 1:8, 1:10 and 1:15 gave the absorption maxima at 370 nm providing a suitable wavelength to work.

Effect of pH: The effect of pH on the stability and intensity of colour was determined by preparing a series of mixtures containing metal and the reagent in the ratio of 1:5 and buffers with pH values varying from 2.0 to 6.8. The wavelength of maximum absorbance and the absorbance at the wavelength maximum remain unchanged between pH 4.0 and 5.2 and thus rigid control of the pH during colour formation is not necessary. A sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer of pH approximately 4.5 gives satisfactory pH control and does not interfere in the determination in any way.

Effect of reagent concentration and stability of colour: The effect of excess of the reagent on the intensity of colour was also studied and it was found that six-fold excess of the reagent is required for full coloration. Under optimum conditions the colour intensity remains unaltered in the temperature range of 15 to 80° in presence of light. The colour develops instantaneously on mixing the reactants and remains stable for more than ten days.

Beer's law, sensitivity and precision: The system adheres to Beer's law in the range of 1.0-60.0 ppm of osmium(VIII) with an optimum range of 5.0-55 ppm of the metal as evaluated from a Ringbom's plot¹³. The molar absorptivity calculated over the range studied is 1429 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ and the mean sensitivity¹⁴ is 0.132 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The average relative deviation as determined of a series of measurements made according to the optimum conditions ranges between ± 0.55 to 1.0%.

Composition and stability constants: The composition and stability constant of the complex as determined by Bjerrum's pH-metric method¹⁵, were found to be 1:1 and 1.26×10^9 , respectively. Spectrophotometric methods could not be applied for stability determination because of the precipitation in the solution containing osmium and cysteine ratio as 1:1, possibly due to the formation of some polymeric species which is perhaps not formed in

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presence of excess of the reagent. Further, the formation curves (\bar{n} vs μA plots) for 1 : 5 and 1 : 10 metal to ligand ratios were found to be identical, thereby confirming the absence of polynuclear species.

Effect of diverse ions : The interference caused by various cations and anions was also studied. Solutions containing a known quantity of Os^{VIII} was also studied. Solutions containing a known quantity of Os^{VIII} and varying amounts of diverse ions were prepared and the osmium was determined. Ammonium, K, Tl^I, Rb, Cs, Ba^{II}, Sr^{II}, Ca^{II}, Mg^{II}, Fe^{II}, Mn^{II}, Zn^{II}, Co^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, Pb^{II}, Fe^{III}, Al^{III}, Sb^{III}, Bi^{III}, Ru^{III}, Rh^{III}, Ir^{III}, Zr^{IV}, Sn^{IV}, Pt^{IV}, Mo^{VI}, W^{VI}, Se^{VI}, Te^{VI}, chloride, bromide, iodide, nitrite, nitrate, chlorate, carbonate, oxalate, sulphate and phosphate ions do not interfere in the determination even when present in five-fold excess. Interference caused by the following ions could be eliminated by the addition of the reagents given in parenthesis, Cu²⁺(thiosulphate), Ag⁺(iodide). Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} ions are tolerated if their concentration is less than osmium ions. However, the presence of Cr^{III} seriously interferes as the colour changes to bluish green.

Recommended procedure : A solution containing osmium(VIII) is treated with a suitable masking agent as necessary, six or more than six-fold excess of an aqueous solution of cysteine is added and the volume is brought to about 60% of the final volume

by adding distilled water. The pH of the solution is then adjusted to about 4.5 by adding a buffer solution, diluted to the requisite volume with distilled water and then the absorbance is measured at 370 nm against water blank.

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